

WHEN DO YOU NEED TO BE CONCERNED ABOUT VEINS?

The skin on your legs, feet and lower part of the legs started to enlarge, inflamed, and swell then you need to be worried about your veins. Because the blood vessels which pump the blood from the legs to the heart become twisted. You need to seek a [vein specialist near me California](#). In critical situations, they even raise up or swell and they are often purple or blue in color.

When the valves in the veins become weakened then veins appear. Inside the legs, healthy veins have a one-way valve that allows the blood to flow up the leg. These veins work against gravity and pump the blood towards the heart. The blood started to pool in the legs when these valves become weakened that causes the pressure to build in the legs. A **vein doctor near me** will give you a proper idea about the vein's condition either spider or varicose veins.

People who are overweight, pregnant, or stand and sit for long periods on regular basis have an increased risk of developing veins. Heredity and aging are also the factors that play a role in veins. The person with these two factors has a higher risk of getting the veins. Contact a **vein doctor near me California**, to decrease the risk of veins.

Some people have veins but they don't have any kind of symptoms in them. Some mild symptoms including swelling, itching over the veins in the feet and ankles can be experienced by people with venous disease. Aching, burning, the sensation of heaviness, tiredness, and pain in the leg are other typical symptoms. After sitting or standing for an extended period of time in the same positions make the symptoms of veins worse.

Some more serious symptoms can be experienced by some people. These symptoms include soreness, bleeding, skin ulcers, blood clots, and continuous pain in the calf area. Changes in the skin such as changes in scaling, skin color, thinning and dryness of skin, and inflammation are the other symptoms of venous disease. You can prevent the critical situation of veins by asking for more symptoms with the **varicose vein treatment in California**.

Veins do not always mean that there is a serious health issue. Having a vein is quite common, there is a rare case when it develops into a more serious health issue, however. This means that the deeper veins are experiencing a blockage and this is known as deep vein thrombosis(DVT).

To diagnose a varicose vein by examining the patient's legs and feet you may need a **vein specialist**. Things for a **vein doctor** will be looking for include changes in skin color, tender areas, swelling, and sores.

In order to reduce the chance of developing veins, there are some preventative measures that you may take. Regular exercise, wearing compression stockings, and elevating the legs on the regular basis are few ways to try to prevent them. To get rid of the vein issues you should make an appointment with [vein treatment California](#).